

OASIS: a mission and science enabler for the Lunar surface.

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Introduction: As interest in Lunar applications shifts towards long-term use cases, the challenges of operating on the Moon's surface are receiving growing attention. In particular, in-situ science and demonstrators will be essential in coming years to better characterize environmental conditions and their effects on systems. However, for missions aiming to operate longer than one lunar day, energy management and thermal constraints during night quickly appear as critical issues. Small- and medium-sized systems are particularly affected, due to strict mass or dimensions constraints, which easily leads to spiraling engineering budgets and mission cost.

OASIS' service approach: OASIS (Outpost for Advanced Scientific Investigation Station) proposes a different approach by offering platform-level functions as a service to users, that is other Lunar surface assets (instruments, demonstrators, rovers, etc). Its core idea is to pool key capabilities for multiple users to reduce their individual complexity, avoid duplication of functions, and allow them to focus on their fundamental mission objectives. The users are not part of the OASIS development but can be changed from mission to mission. OASIS is thus a self-sustainable system that provides power generation, energy storage and a communication link for up to four users. By using orbital relays (Moonlight constellation), OASIS can improve the data rate and availability of communications –also enabling far side operation– while offloading the hardware and protocol processing burden from users. More importantly, its integrated energy storage ensures power provision during eclipse periods, thereby enabling Lunar night survival.

OASIS overview and use cases: OASIS aims to be a compact and moderate-mass system (sub-200 kg and 1m³) with a minimum operating lifetime of 2 years. To allow more flexibility with respect to accommodation and transport, the system is composed of two individual boxes, linked by a harness. Its interfaces to users include deployable power and data harnesses, enabling a minimum deployment distance of 6 meters. In its first configuration, OASIS is meant to be installed on a lander where it will remain, while still supporting users offloading (see *Figure 1*). Targetted landing latitudes are south polar and near-polar.

Figure 1: Notional OASIS (in yellow) use case, here with a lander and payloads deployed on the surface.

However, the design of OASIS is developed with modularity in mind, both with respect to its equipment and use cases. Namely, it is compatible with evolutions of its energy storage and extendible harness. In addition, further use cases are being considered, where OASIS is either moved once on the surface, or mounted on a rover from launch.

OASIS is thought to be a recurring mission, the overall objective is thus to offer a versatile platform, able to support varied users and missions scenarios.